

Medical Certificate Anomalies: Analysis of Central Medical Inspection Missions and Medico-Legal Implications in Tunisia

Fourati Hazem^{1,2*}, Moussi Hanen³, Shimi Maha^{1,2}, Elkhel Mohamed Cherif¹

¹Department of Forensic Medicine, Military Hospital of Tunis, Tunis, Tunisia

²Faculty of Medicine of Tunis, University Tunis El Manar, Tunis, Tunisia

³Faculty of Medicine of Monastir, University of Monastir, Monastir, Tunisia

ABSTRACT

Introduction:

The medical certificate is a medico-legal document that fully engages the professional responsibility of the physician. Errors in its issuance, whether due to lack of knowledge of certification rules or acts of collusion, can have disciplinary, civil, and criminal consequences. The aim of this study was to analyze anomalies in medical certificates identified during the missions of the Central Medical Inspection and to evaluate their medico-legal implications.

Methods:

This was a retrospective descriptive study based on reports from medical inspection missions conducted in the Tunis region between January 1 and December 31, 2023. All reports concerning medical certificates issued by physicians that contained anomalies were included. Certificates falsified by non-physicians were excluded. Data collected included the source and reason for the complaint, type of certificate, physician's practice sector, observed anomalies, and inspection conclusions.

Results:

A total of 149 inspection missions were analyzed, involving 160 medical certificates. Among these, 55 certificates issued by physicians contained anomalies. Complaints mainly concerned suspected collusive certificates (38 cases) or falsifications (17 cases). Certificates of sick leave accounted for the majority of affected documents (42 cases). Identified anomalies included formal defects (lack of physician or patient identification, missing signature or stamp), inconsistencies in clinical content, and administrative irregularities, particularly lack of traceability in some public institutions. Following the inspections, 38 certificates were classified as collusive, while 17 anomalies were attributed to lack of knowledge of certification rules.

Conclusion:

Anomalies in medical certificates remain frequent and expose physicians to significant medico-legal risk. Strengthening training and awareness regarding proper certificate issuance is essential to improve the quality of these documents.

KEYWORDS: medical certificate, medical inspection, medico-legal responsibility, medical ethics

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:

04 May 2026

Available on:

<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

The medical certificate is a fundamental medico-legal document intended to certify medical facts observed during the examination of a patient. Its issuance engages the disciplinary, civil, and criminal responsibility of the issuing physician, in accordance with the Tunisian Code of Medical

Ethics and applicable legal provisions [1–3]. In daily practice, physicians are frequently requested to issue medical certificates for administrative, social, or judicial purposes, which increases the risk of errors or breaches.

Several studies have shown that the preparation of medical certificates remains an important source of medico-legal

Medical Certificate Anomalies: Analysis of Central Medical Inspection Missions and Medico-Legal Implications in Tunisia

disputes, both in high-income and middle-income countries [2–4]. In Tunisia, complaints to the medical councils related to inaccurate or collusive certificates account for a substantial portion of disputes involving physicians [4].

At the international level, recent studies have highlighted the persistence of major errors in various types of medical certificates, particularly death certificates and work incapacity certificates, with error rates sometimes exceeding 50% [5,6]. These findings underscore the inadequacy of both initial and continuing training in medical certificate preparation.

The Central Medical Inspection plays a key role in monitoring the compliance of medical acts, including certificate issuance. However, data generated from these inspections remain underutilized for scientific purposes.

The objective of this study was to identify the main anomalies in medical certificates observed during medical inspection investigations conducted in 2023 in the Tunis region and to analyze their medico-legal implications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a retrospective descriptive study based on medical inspection reports produced by the Medical Inspection Directorate of the Ministry of Health in the Tunis region between January 1 and December 31, 2023.

All inspection reports concerning medical certificates issued by physicians that were subject to complaints or suspected irregularities were included. Certificates falsified by non-physicians, which did not fall under professional medical responsibility, were excluded.

Collected data included the source and reason for the complaint, type of medical certificate, practice sector of the issuing physician, identified anomalies, and conclusions of the inspection.

Access to the archives was authorized by the Ministry of Health. Anonymity of patients and physicians was strictly maintained.

Data were analyzed descriptively by calculating frequencies and percentages for the various variables studied.

RESULTS

Inspection Activities

During the study period, 149 medical inspection missions were conducted in the Tunis region. These missions involved 160 medical certificates that had been subject to complaints or reports. Among these certificates, 55 certificates issued by physicians presented anomalies and constituted the study population analyzed in this work (figure 1).

Figure 1: Medical inspection reports verifying the authenticity of medical certificates.

Reasons for Complaints

The main reason for complaints was suspicion of collusive medical certificates in 38 cases and suspicion of falsification in 17 cases (Figure 2).

Medical Certificate Anomalies: Analysis of Central Medical Inspection Missions and Medico-Legal Implications in Tunisia

Figure 2: Reason for the complaint

Types of Certificates Involved

Sick leave certificates were the most frequently implicated documents, accounting for 76% of cases (Table 1).

Table 1: Types of Medical Certificates Involved

Type of Certificate	Number	Percentage
Sick Leave Certificate	42	76%
Initial Medical Certificates	9	16%
Extended Sick Leave Certificates	3	6%
Prenuptial Certificate	1	2%
Total	55	100%

Characteristics of the Issuing Physicians

The physicians who issued the medical certificates in this study belonged to the public sector in 28 cases (51%) and to the private sector in 27 cases (49%) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Information on the Physicians Who Issued the Certificates

Nature of Observed Anomalies

The anomalies identified during inspections could be categorized into three main types:

- **Formal anomalies**
- **Clinical content anomalies**

- **Administrative irregularities**

Formal anomalies primarily involved physician identification (5/55, 9%) and patient identification (6/55, 11%), missing signatures or stamps (5/55, 9% and 4/55, 7%, respectively), and non-compliance with regulatory templates (2/55, 4%).

Medical Certificate Anomalies: Analysis of Central Medical Inspection Missions and Medico-Legal Implications in Tunisia

Content anomalies mainly consisted of discrepancies between clinical findings and the prescribed duration of sick leave. In two initial medical certificates, lesion descriptions differed from the medical registry, and one sick leave certificate showed a mismatch between the patient's clinical condition and the recommended management.

Administrative irregularities were mostly related to lack of traceability: 25 patients received a sick leave certificate without registration, 27 certificates were not recorded in the medical registry, and some receipts or copies were not archived. Adherence to duty schedules was also limited, with five certificates issued by physicians not assigned according to the official schedule.

Inspection Outcomes

Following the investigations, 38 certificates were classified as collusive and 17 anomalies were attributed to lack of knowledge of medical certificate rules

Recommendations from the Medical Inspection Team

At the end of the investigation, the inspection team made several recommendations. Three cases were closed without further action (5.5%), while first-degree sanctions were proposed: a formal warning in 14 cases (25.5%), a caution in 16 cases (29.1%), and a reprimand in 8 cases (14.5%). Second-degree sanctions were issued by the Disciplinary Council for 18 physicians (32.7%). Furthermore, inspection reports were sent to the National Council of the Order of Physicians in Tunis in 20 cases (36.4%) and to the Legal and Litigation Unit in 32 cases (58.2%) to ensure proper follow-up on professional and legal responsibilities.

DISCUSSION

This study highlights the frequency and diversity of anomalies in medical certificate issuance, confirming that this act remains a high medico-legal risk. Our findings align with medico-legal literature emphasizing the central role of medical certificates in engaging the disciplinary, civil, and criminal liability of physicians [2,3,7,8].

The main limitation of this study is its retrospective nature and the relatively small sample size, which does not allow extrapolation to national practices. Nevertheless, the originality of data obtained from the Central Medical Inspection provides a valuable institutional and practical perspective rarely documented in the literature.

Sick leave certificates represented the majority of implicated documents in our series. This predominance is consistent with observations reported by Khalfallah, who identified these certificates as a major source of complaints to the medical council in Tunisia [4]. Their socio-professional and financial impact likely explains the frequency of disputes and suspicions of collusion.

The high proportion of certificates classified as collusive illustrates a persistent problem of ignorance or transgression of ethical rules. Issuing a collusive certificate constitutes a

serious offense under the Tunisian Code of Medical Ethics [1] and exposes the practitioner to disciplinary sanctions, potentially including temporary suspension. Under criminal law, Tunisian legislation provides severe sanctions for inaccurate or fraudulent certificates, particularly when issued by healthcare professionals in the course of their duties [9–11].

Administrative anomalies observed, particularly in the public sector, highlight the importance of traceability of medical acts. The lack of patient registration, medical records, or administrative documentation constitutes a breach of the operating rules of public health institutions and may engage the administrative and civil liability of the issuing physician [9,10]. These findings align with recommendations from professional and medico-legal authorities, which emphasize systematic retention of medical records and copies of issued certificates [1,8].

At the international level, recent studies have shown that certification errors remain extremely frequent. Sharma et al. reported that 99% of analyzed death certificates contained at least one error [5], while other studies found error rates exceeding 50% [5,10], confirming the universal nature of the problem.

Several studies have demonstrated that structured interventions combining targeted physician training, standardized tools, and regular audits can significantly improve the quality of medical certification, as illustrated by the Data for Health initiative, which reported a notable reduction in errors in death certification following the implementation of tailored educational strategies [3,12,13].

CONCLUSION

Anomalies in medical certificates remain frequent and constitute a major source of medico-legal liability for physicians. Strengthening continuing education programs focused on proper certificate writing and ethical obligations is essential to prevent collusive certificates and improve the quality of medical practice.

REFERENCES

- I. Code de Déontologie Médicale tunisien. Décret n° 93-1155 du 17 mai 1993, portant code de déontologie médicale. J.O.R.T n° 40 des 28 mai et 1er juin 1993 page 764.
- II. Epain D. Certificats médicaux et urgence-certificats de coups et blessures. EMC-Médecine. 2005;2(4):448–467.
- III. Nseme E, Eone DH, Sando Z, Ngankol VM, Sosso MA, Ashuntantang G. Mise au Point sur la Rédaction des Certificats Médicaux et Médico-légaux. Health sciences and diseases. 2018;19(2).
- IV. Khalfallah M. Responsabilité déontologique du médecin certificateur: Analyse des plaintes déposées

Medical Certificate Anomalies: Analysis of Central Medical Inspection Missions and Medico-Legal Implications in Tunisia

- au conseil régional de l'ordre des médecins de Tunis.2017.
- V. Sharma, N., Singh, M., Bahurupi, Y. et al. Analysis of errors in medical certificates of cause of death (MCCD) at a tertiary care institute in 2022. *Discov Public Health* 21, 85 (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12982-024-00209-7>
- VI. Agyekum F, Asamoah IE, Bashir M, Asante NA, Ganatra K, Duodu F, Akumiah FK, Brodie-Mends D, Asamoah KT, Ampofo EB, Doku A. Assessment of errors in death certification and mortality patterns and trends among medical patients at Korle Bu Teaching Hospital, 2019-2023. *Ghana Med J.* 2025 Sep;59(3):111-120. doi: 10.4314/gmj.v59i3.2. PMID: 41122261; PMCID: PMC12536572.
- VII. Quatrehomme G, Alunni V, Martrille L. Item no 9. Certificats médicaux. *La Revue de Médecine Légale.* 2018
- VIII. Boissin H, Rougemont D. Les certificats médicaux– Règles générales d'établissement. CNO; 2006.
- IX. Ministère de la Santé publique. Circulaire n° 71/2000 du 11 septembre 2000 relative à la délivrance du CMI en cas d'accidents du travail et maladies professionnelles.
- X. Décret N° 81-1634 du 30 Novembre 1981, portant règlement général intérieur des Hôpitaux, Instituts et Centres Spécialisés relevant du Ministère de la Santé Publique.
- XI. Code_des_obligations_et_des_contrats.pdf [Internet]. [16 Jan 2019]. Disponible à l'URL: [http://www.e-justice.tn/fileadmin/fichiers_site_francais/codes juridiques/Code_des_obligations_et_des_contrats.pdf](http://www.e-justice.tn/fileadmin/fichiers_site_francais/codes_juridiques/Code_des_obligations_et_des_contrats.pdf)
- XII. Code_penal_12_07_2010_fr.pdf. [16 Jan 2019]. Disponible à l'URL: [http://www.e-justice.tn/fileadmin/fichiers_site_francais/ codes juridiques/ Code_penal_12_07_2010_fr.pdf](http://www.e-justice.tn/fileadmin/fichiers_site_francais/codes_juridiques/Code_penal_12_07_2010_fr.pdf)
- XIII. Abeygunasekara A, Ramasundara M. Evaluation of errors in death certification by medical officers in an acute hospital. *Australas J Ageing.* 2023 Dec;42(4):786-790. doi: 10.1111/ajag.13207. Epub 2023 May 1. PMID: 37127432.
- XIV. Hart, J.D., Sorchik, R., Bo, K.S. et al. Improving medical certification of cause of death: effective strategies and approaches based on experiences from the Data for Health Initiative. *BMC Med* 18, 74 (2020).<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-020-01519-8>